

HYSTERETIC BEHAVIOUR MODELING OF WOVEN FABRIC UNDER LARGE STRAIN

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ABSTRACT

The constant evolution of the use of composite materials in the field of aerospace, aeronautics or automotive induces many challenges during the process phases of the composites. Particularly during the forming phase through RTM (Resin Transfer Moulding) process for dry fabrics or thermo – stamping process for prepregs. Due to the complexity of the new geometries, it is important to be able to handle new phenomena such as energy dissipation induced by the friction between fibers. Moreover, some recent studies have shown a new way to preform composite reinforcements by following incremental forming instead of the usual well-known forming. Incremental forming consists to use more than one punch and imposed different sequences in order to reduce defect on the final part such as wrinkles, residual stresses, shear angle, etc. This new forming method is still under the beginning of research and need to be more studied. Experimentally and numerically, it is possible to show huge shear angle and curvature variations which could be cyclical. Given these new studies about incremental forming and given these new geometries, cyclic loading (i.e. loading & unloading phases) in shearing and bending modes may appear; and the existing models, being for the most part hyperelastic, are not enough reliable to simulate such processes in a realistic way. Indeed, experimentally it is possible to observe a hysteretic behaviour of the material during the unloading phase. The purpose of this paper is then to describe the dissipative phenomenon from shearing and bending effects between yarns at a macroscopic scale. The model proposed here makes possible to consider the dissipative phenomenon during the load phase but also the hysteretic path during the discharge. Finally, this model can be integrated into a finite element software as a constitutive behaviour law to make more reliable simulations.

1 INTRODUCTION

As industrial interest in composite materials continues to grow, it is important to propose new and innovative techniques to better understand, experiment and simulate this type of material. Indeed, until now, industrial demand has been limited to simple geometries, thus techniques and associated models have been developed according to different fundamental assumptions. As an example, it is possible to mention the highly appreciated hyperelastic models [1-5]. These models are relatively simple and do not require many parameters to operate. Their application and integration into finite element calculation software is simple and fast. The identification phase is not long and is usually very direct. However, the aerospace, aeronautics, automotive and medical industries are increasingly interested in developing parts with complex geometries [6-9]. This specific interest in complex geometries necessarily faces many constraints. Indeed, complex geometries induce new phenomena that were not necessarily existing before. For example, cyclic variations of shear angle or curvature may occur. A cyclic variation is characterized by two phases: a loading phase and an unloading phase. This cyclic effect can occur several times, leading to multicyclic loading (Fig. 3b). From an experimental point of view, a shear test following a multi-cyclic loading is presented on fig. 3a and shows a major difference between the loading and unloading phases (Fig. 3b). Indeed, a dissipative part takes place during the loading phase and a hysteretic part takes place during the discharge for any loading amplitude (Fig. 3b). This very interesting and important phenomenon must be described and modelled in order to be used for industrial application through finite element calculations to simulate the forming process of composite materials. Indeed, it allows both to describe the loading phase, as hyperelastic models do, but also to describe the

unloading phase, which is extremely often very different from the loading phase. In addition, cyclic variations occur not only in complex geometries but also in simple shaping. Indeed, the use of blank holder induces a cyclic variation in bending. In addition, in 2018, work was published [8] stipulates that to meet industrial demand on complex geometries, a new shaping method can be used. The incremental shaping, which consists in no longer transforming the fabric or thermoplastic at once but in carrying out complex sequencing. [8] also shows that depending on the sequences, the final geometry of the part may be different, either better or worse than using the usual shaping with a single punch. In addition, defects such as folds, residual stresses, high shear angles can also be different. Moreover, some recent work is beginning to focus on the characteristics of the part once in service. If cyclic loading occurs and hyperelastic models have been used, then the simulation results cannot be considered since they do not represent the physical condition of the material. Indeed, the residual stresses are not at all the same if a hyperelastic model or a dissipative model is used. To explain this phenomenon and present model, this paper is constructed as following: the first part is about the general assumptions to model the dissipative and hysteretic behaviour. The second part concerns the model itself through an experimental approach, a description of the dissipative model and a description of the hysteretic behaviour. Some works have already be done but for metal materials [13, 15-17] or under the assumption of small strains [18]. The method presented in this paper is following the assumptions of large stains. The third part presents some results and simulation analysis.

2 GENERAL ASSUMPTIONS FOR MODELISATION

In order to characterise and simulate the dissipative behaviour of a composite material, the study, carried out by this article, is based on dry fabrics. Furthermore, the study is held under the macroscopic scale, in which the fabric can be considered as a continuous material. This hypothesis makes possible to perform faster simulations with an overall description of the defects (wrinkles, shear angle, buckling, etc.) and fibre orientations. However, it is not be possible to access on more localised information such as local buckling of yarns, distortions or others. Moreover, the deformation modes of the composite materials are assumed to be decoupled, therefore they do not influence each other (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Decoupling of deformation modes: membrane and out of plane modes (In plane shear and Elongation – Bending). Differentiation between dissipative and elastic modes.

This allows to be able, at first, to describe the evolution of each mode and then to quantify their influence on the result. Finally, carbon or glass fibres are considered almost inextensible due to the high tensile rigidity. This induces that the mode of traction compression of the fibres is elastic. Considering these previous assumptions, the shear dissipation mode follows a pure shear kinematics. Finally, only in-plane shear and bending modes dissipate energy mainly due to friction between fibres. In this paper, in-plane shear mode is described following thermodynamics rules and bending is described following an empirical approach. As usual for describing plasticity effect, the assumption of the intermediate theory [12, 14] (Fig. 2) is applied. This theory leads to decompose the total transformation gradient and the Green Lagrange tensor in two terms: one elasticity contribution and one plasticity contribution.

Figure 2: Intermediate theory: decomposition elastic/plasticity tensors [12, 14].

By using this intermediate theory and by using the well-known additive and multiplicative decompositions such as Kröner – Lee [10] (Eq. 1) and Green – Naghdi [11] (Eq. 2) adapted for anisotropic material, it is possible to define every tensors needed for the model. Finally, to develop a first approach of modelisation, it is supposed here that the stress and strain are already integrated in the thickness of the fabric. The model is therefore reliable for think fabric such as dry fabric or thin interlock (Hexcel® G1151 for example). -

3 MODELISATION OF THE DISSIPATIVE AND HYSTERETIC BEHAVIOUR

In this section, both in-plane shear and bending are describing. In-plane shear is following thermodynamic principles. On the contrary, bending mode is an empirical approach. Firstly, experimental data are shown. The last part presents some results and comparison between modelisation, finite element simulations and experimental results.

3.1 Experimental approach for in-plane shear and bending modes

To characterise in-plane shear mode, the best experimental set up can be either Picture Frame Test or Bias Extension Test. Since, the hypothesis of non-elongation of the fibre and since, the shear angle might be considered constant during a Picture Frame Test, this test is the most adapted. The experimental set-up and data are shown Fig. 3. Furthermore, concerning the bending mode, the cantilever and three points bending sets up are not adapted since it is necessary to apply cyclic loads to get the dissipative behaviour. The purpose is then to model the behaviour of the material after a Kawabata test, which gives the possibility to impose cyclic loading. The bending behaviour of Hexcel® G1151 is from De Bilbao works [19].

Figure 3: In-plane shear behaviour of Hexcel® G1151. (a): Picture frame test set-up | (b): Material behaviour (dissipative and hysteretic).

As it is possible to see in Fig. 3b, during cyclic loading, the path is different during a charge and during a discharge. The hysteretic behaviour of the material during the discharge is clearly present and must be modelised for the reasons explained below in the introduction. The strategy to modelise such a behaviour is to link a usual dissipative model like plasticity during a load and an old theory initially developed by Mroz in 1967 [16] during unloading phase. This theory is based on nested surfaces. The problem of such a model is the number of parameters to identify which is directly proportional to the number of nested surfaces. Therefore, a new description has been made using fractional derivatives. This new description is mathematically more difficult but much easier to apply since it needs few parameters to work.

The behaviour is almost the same for bending mode. Fig. 4 represents the behaviour of the Hexcel® G1151 material for a load (Fig. 4b) and the hysteretic behaviour is supposed to follow the results given from a Kawabata test (Fig. 4a and Fig. 4c).

Figure 4: Bending behaviour of Hexcel® G1151. (a): Kawabata experimental set-up [19] | (b): material behavior [19] | (c): Hysteretic prediction of the material.

Contrary to the modelisation for in-plane shear mode, the model presented for bending is purely empirical. It is a choice to show the feasibility and simplicity of the fractional derivatives method which can be applied either for constitutive model or empirical model.

3.2 Constitutive modelisation for in-plane shear

The in-plane shear is following the thermodynamics rules. To describe such a model, three quantities must be defined:

- A potential a free energy, which give the dissipative law after being derivated.
- A plasticity criterion which give the information of the actual state of the material. Three states are possible: elasticity, plasticity or the boundary between both. To choose which state the material is following, an elastic prediction is firstly made. If the plasticity criterion is negative, then the material state is elastic, if the criterion is positive, it is therefore dissipative (plasticity) and if it is equal to zero, the state is in the boundary. If the state is in the boundary or the criterion is negative, no dissipative effect appears. If it is positive, dissipation takes place and a plastic flow must be defined and used.
- A plastic flow rule which give the direction of the plastic flow. It gives the shortest way to reach the boundary of the criterion.

Moreover, by using Kröner – Lee [10] and Green – Naghdi [11] decompositions (respectively multiplicative and additive) and the theory of the intermediate configuration, it is therefore possible to describe a model in total lagrangian which is very interesting since every quantities are referred to the initial state of the material where everything is known.

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_e \cdot \mathbf{F}_p \quad (1)$$

Eq. 1 shows the multiplicative decomposition of Kröner – Lee where \mathbf{F} is the transformation gradient tensor, \mathbf{F}_e and \mathbf{F}_p are respectively the elastic and plastic (dissipative) part of the tensor.

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_e + \mathbf{E}_p \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2 shows the additive decomposition of Green – Naghdi adapted for anisotropic materials where \mathbf{E} is the Green – Lagrange strain tensor, \mathbf{E}_e and \mathbf{E}_p are respectively the elastic and plastic (dissipative) part of this tensor.

By coupling these two equations (Eq. 1 and Eq. 2), it is possible to define every tensor necessary to define the potential of free energy. Moreover, as it was said during the assumptions, two types of phenomenon may appear during a forming process. In-plane shear is an in-plane transformation as elongation mode. The first step is therefore to describe the potential of free energy using the assumptions made before. As it was said, the in-plane shear dissipation mode follows a pure shear kinematics (since the fibres do not elongate Fig 5b) and the associated tensor is following:

$$\mathbf{F}_p = \cos\left(\frac{\gamma_p}{2}\right) \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_1 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_1 + \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2) + \sin\left(\frac{\gamma_p}{2}\right) \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_1 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2 + \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_1) \quad (3)$$

Where γ_p is the dissipative part of the total shear angle, $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_{1,2}$ are the direction of the yarns in the initial configuration of the material defined Fig 5a.

Figure 5: Pure shear kinematics. (a): Initial state of the fabric | (b): Kinematics of the dissipative in-plane shear mode | (c): Relaxed state of the material after being sheared.

By using Eq. 1, Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 it is possible to define every quantity and the most important the elastic part of the Green – Lagrange tensor. This is this tensor which is used to define the potential of free energy as a usual form. It is possible to define such potential since the model is in total lagrangian. It implies that the dissipation is directly considering in the definition of the elastic part of the Green – Lagrange tensor defined by Eq. 4.

$$\mathbf{E}_e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{F}_p^t \cdot (\mathbf{F}_e^t \cdot \mathbf{F}_e - \mathbf{I}_d) \cdot \mathbf{F}_p) \quad (4)$$

\mathbf{I}_d is the second order identity tensor. As is it possible to see in Eq. 4. this unusual definition of the tensor \mathbf{E}_e leads to put back every quantity into the initial configuration. Therefore, a usual quadratic form of a potential can be written:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[K_1 \cdot \left(\mathbf{E}_e : (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_1 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_1) \right)^2 + K_2 \cdot \left(\mathbf{E}_e : (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_2 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2) \right)^2 \right] + \\ \frac{1}{2} \cdot K_{sh} \cdot \left(\mathbf{E}_e : (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_1 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_2) \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot K_{sh} \cdot \left(\mathbf{E}_e : (\bar{\mathbf{G}}_2 \otimes \bar{\mathbf{G}}_1) \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

From this description it is possible to define the evolution of its dual which is the Piola – Kirchhoff II tensor denoted \mathbf{S} (Eq. 6) by decoupling the elongation terms and the in-plane shear terms. This stress tensor \mathbf{S} comes from the derivation of the potential of free energy in the elastic strains space.

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial E_{eij}} = \mu \cdot (\mathbf{E}_e : (\bar{G}_i \otimes \bar{G}_j)) \cdot K_{ij} \quad (6)$$

Where \mathbf{K} is defined Eq. 7.

$$\mathbf{K} = K_1 \cdot (\bar{G}_1 \otimes \bar{G}_1) + K_2 \cdot (\bar{G}_2 \otimes \bar{G}_2) + K_{sh} \cdot (\bar{G}_1 \otimes \bar{G}_2 + \bar{G}_2 \otimes \bar{G}_1) \quad (7)$$

Where K_1 , K_2 and K_{sh} are respectively the weft, warp and shear angle modulus. μ is the surface density of the material.

From Eq. 6 it is possible to define a yield criterion following the rule and principle of maximal dissipation such as:

$$\mathcal{D} = \mathbf{S} : \dot{\mathbf{E}}_p \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\dot{\mathbf{E}}_p = \lambda \cdot \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{S})}{\partial \mathbf{S}} = \frac{\dot{\gamma}_p}{2} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\gamma_p}{2}\right) \cdot (\bar{G}_1 \otimes \bar{G}_2 + \bar{G}_2 \otimes \bar{G}_1) \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the yield criterion can be defined as following:

$$\phi(\mathbf{S}) = |(\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{X}(\gamma)) : (\bar{G}_1 \otimes \bar{G}_2 + \bar{G}_2 \otimes \bar{G}_1)| - (S_y + \alpha(\gamma)) \quad (10)$$

The parameter λ in Eq. 9 represents the plastic multiplier. In Eq.10, \mathbf{X} represents the center of the surface, S_y the limit of elasticity and α the size of the surface. \mathbf{X} and α depend on the shear angle which means that the size and the position of the surface are proportionally linked to the shear angle. Both of these quantities represents, respectively, the kinematics and the isotropic hardening of the material. This criterion is reliable enough to describe a load but not a discharge. Indeed, it represents only dissipation and plasticity effect. It is therefore necessary to improve this model (See Fig. 6). The first solution is to add nested surfaces inside the surface defined Eq. 10 and presented Fig. 6b. However, despite this method is very efficient, it needs a lot of parameters to identify to manage the evolution of each nested surface. This is why a new method is proposed here using fractional derivative.

Figure 6: Yield criterion, graphic representation in the Piola – Kirchhoff II stress space. (a): Initial formulation with one surface | (b): Model with two nested surfaces and their own evolution laws.

To reduce the number of parameters to identify the idea is to use the fractional derivatives method instead of nested surfaces. Demonstration is not shown in this paper, just the result is presented and discussed. For a load or a charge, the model is the same as before. When cyclical variations appear, the model is following other rules defined on Eq. 11.

$$S_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot S_j + \mu \cdot K_{sh} \cdot \left[\sum_{m=0}^3 B_m |S_j|^m \right] \cdot \text{sign}(\gamma - \gamma_j) \cdot \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \cdot |\gamma - \gamma_j|^{1-\alpha} \quad (11)$$

Eq. 11 is only available when the load is situated between the upper and lower boundary presented on Fig. 7. Otherwise, the formulation presented above is used. In Eq. 11 several variables appear such as:

- S_j is the stress state of the material just before the fractional derivatives model is applied
- B_m are polynomial parameters to describe the evolution law of the fractional derivatives depending on S_j
- $\Gamma(x)$ is the usual gamma function frequently used when fractional derivatives are employed
- α is the order of the fractional derivative. It can take any value between zero and one

As it is possible to see in Fig. 7 the fractional derivatives are a very reliable and performant method to modelise hysteretic behaviour of a material. Moreover, it does not need too much parameters to work. Fig. 7 represents a comparison between experimental, nested surfaces and fractional derivatives models. Nested surfaces model needed more than fifty parameters to work. Fractional derivative one only needs 9 parameters to perform.

Figure 7: In-plane shear behaviour simulation. Comparison between fractional derivatives and nested surfaces methods.

As it is possible to see in Fig. 7, the three first loops are simulated with either fractional derivatives or nested surfaces methods. The fourth loop only with fractional derivatives and the last loop only with nested surfaces. Is it important to notice that for small shear angle both methods are reliable. However when the shear angle starts to increase, the fractional derivatives method, in addition to requiring fewer parameters, is more suitable.

3.3 Constitutive modelisation for bending

As it was said before, the model presented here is purely empirical. As the model for in-plane shear, the purpose here is to combine two models, one to describe the dissipative effect and one to describe hysteretic loops. It is therefore possible to define three phases depending on the curvature and moment state of the material. For each phase, the model is different:

$$M = \begin{cases} M_{max} \cdot \left(1 - e^{\left(-\frac{C}{K}\right)}\right) & \text{if } |C| \geq |C_{max}| \text{ or } |M_{prev}| > |M_{max}| \\ M_j + \left[\sum_{m=0}^8 B_m |C|^m \right] \cdot \text{sign}(C - C_j) \cdot \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \cdot |C - C_j|^{1-\alpha} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The result once this model integrated into a finite element calculation software leads to the result presented Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Bending behaviour simulation by using fractional derivative.

4 APPLICATIONS AND SIMULATIONS

Once these two models integrated onto a finite element calculation software and parameters identified, it is possible to make some simulation and discuss about the results. The first simulation of forming made is the very well-known hemisphere. The second one is a more complex shape that can be considered as a four branches cross.

Figure 9: Hemisphere simulations and experiment. (a): Dissipative model | (b): Hyperelastic model | (c): Experimental set-up and result [20].

As is it possible to see in Fig. 8 there is no significant differences between hyperelastic and dissipative model for simple loads such as hemisphere forming. Indeed, there is no cyclical variation of load either in bending or in-plane shear. This simulation leads to validate the dissipative model since it gives the same result as hyperelastic and same result as the experimental test.

Figure 10: Four branches cross simulations and experiment. (a): Dissipative model | (b): Hyperelastic model | (c): Experimental set-up and result.

In this case, it is possible to see very huge difference between hyperelastic model and dissipative. Indeed, to make this form, incremental forming was used by doing at first two punches (in diagonal) and then the two other ones. Following this sequence cyclic variation in bending and in-plane shear appear. This leads to difficult loads on the fabric and then dissipative model is more reliable than hyperelastic ones.

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, through this paper it is shown that dissipative modelisation of material can be much more reliable and efficiency if the forming process includes difficult geometries or needs to follow incremental processes. Indeed, new phenomenon may appear and usual hyperelastic models are not enough rich to describe the reality. From a general point of view, considering energy dissipation might be useful in engineering domain since the defects of the final part are more realistic. Indeed, it is possible to consider the general defaults such as wrinkle, buckling and high shear angle but it is also possible to know the mechanical state of the part once it has been formed. Recent works have shown interest of the study of residual stresses inside the part to check the feasibility and the behaviour of the part once in service. Moreover, the industrial needs are still growing up and challenges are more and more complexes. Incremental forming and boundary conditions management are off major importance and therefore, dissipative model as well.

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